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ESiWACE3 Newsletter

Issue #3 / February 2024

News

8th ENES HPC workshop

The 8th edition of the HPC workshop of the [European Network for Earth System modelling](#) (ENES), organised by ESiWACE3, has already dates!

The event will be held at the [Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change](#) (Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici, CMCC) facilities in Lecce (Italy) on 22-24 May 2024.

The workshop will be structured into four sessions:

- Session 1: European and International Landscape; conveners: Joachim Biercamp (DKRZ) and Erwan Raffin (Eviden/ATOS);
- Session 2: Performance and accelerators; conveners: Mario Acosta (BSC) and Sophie Valcke (CERFACS);
- Session 3: Data; conveners: Uwe Fladrich (SMHI) and Sandro Fiore (UNITrento);
- Session 4: Machine learning; conveners: Peter Dueben (ECMWF) and Giovanni Aloisio (CMCC).

More information about the agenda, the speakers, the registration process and the deadlines will be published soon. Stay tuned!

Coming soon

Save the Date

22-24 May 2024
CMCC Lecce (Italy)

8th ENES HPC WORKSHOP

Sessions:

1. European and International Landscape
2. Performance and accelerators
3. Data
4. Machine Learning

Joint workshop on digital twins at HiPEAC24

The ESIWACE3 Consortium participated in the HiPEAC conference this past January 2024 in Munich, with the workshop “[Towards reliable Digital Twin: advancing applications and tools capabilities for Global Challenges](#)” co-organised together with the Center of Excellence [HiDALGO2](#). The event took place on the afternoon of 17 January 2024 in the Leibniz Rechenzentrum (LRZ). The aim was to allow participants to acquire diverse techniques for constructing efficient simulation systems in Global Systems Science.

The workshop was structured into four segments: application, performance, uncertainty quantification, and portal. The ESIWACE3 member Xavier Yepes-Arbós (BSC) contributed to the performance segment presenting “How to tackle the improvement of computational performance? Different possible ways explored in ESIWACE3”.

Read more [here](#).

Call for Proposals 2024-2025 - Service 2

A new [Call for Proposals](#) (CfP) has just been published!

The call for Service 2, “Services on state-of-the-art development tools for Weather and Climate”, aims to support the exascale preparations for the European Earth System Models (ESM) community. With this new service, the ESIWACE3 Consortium expects to establish collaborative projects in which the ESIWACE experts provide advice and engineering efforts to the applicant. Apart from offering limited engineering time and implementing code modifications, the projects aim to provide guidance and establish knowledge transfer between HPC experts and modelling groups.

The call will run from **4 March 2024** until **3 June 2024** at 14:00h CEST.

The call is open to all European groups developing and maintaining ESM codes. The only requirement is that the applicant’s institutions be located in one of the countries participating in the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking.

Read more [here](#).

ESIWACE3 at the EuroHPC Summit 2024

This year, ESIWACE3 will attend the [EuroHPC Summit 2024](#), which will be held in Antwerp (Belgium) from 18 to 21 March 2024. The aim of the meeting is to bring together the main European supercomputing stakeholders, public and private, as well as decision-makers, allowing them to share the latest technological advances, define synergies, express their current and future needs, and participate in shaping the future of European supercomputing.

ESIWACE3 will participate at the event in many different formats, such as sharing successes in terms of collaborations and synergies between NCCs/CoEs, fishbowling to present the services provided by our experts and speed dating with whoever could be interested in learning more about the CoE. Also, a poster presenting the main objectives and the project's services catalogue will be displayed during the event.

Events

Internal events

2nd ESIWACE3 General Assembly

ESIWACE3 held its 2nd General Assembly on 27 and 28 November 2023. Organised in virtual format by the leading institution Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), the event consisted of two half days. On the afternoon of 27 November, the Consortium reviewed the status of the project, while on the morning of the 28 November, the management team invited several external speakers who presented and deepened into some initiatives potentially interesting for the Consortium. The meeting concluded with dedicated sessions on management and coordination, as well as breakout group time to discuss some internal decisions.

Taking advantage of the event, the BSC published a [news item](#) about the new phase of ESIWACE, highlighting the change of leadership with respect to the previous phases and the latest objectives of this 3rd phase. The prestigious American HPC-related magazine [HPCwire](#) echoed the [piece](#), contributing to spreading the knowledge of the project beyond Europe.

Read more [here](#).

External events

External events in which ESIWACE3 has participated since the last issue of the ESIWACE Newsletter:

- [RSE Conference](#), Swansea (UK), 5 September 2023. [Presentation](#).
- [20th ECMWF Workshop](#), Bologna (Italy), 9-13 October 2023. [Poster](#).
- [NCAR Workshop](#), Boulder (CO, USA), 9-10 November 2023. [Invited talk](#).
- [NCAR Workshop](#), Boulder (CO, USA), 9-10 November 2023. [Presentation](#).
- [SuperComputing23](#), Denver (DE, USA), 12-17 November 2023. [Tutorial](#) & [Video](#).
- [Bits&Chips Event](#), Eindhoven (Netherlands), 10 December 2023. [Presentation](#).
- [HiPEAC 2024](#), Munich (Germany), 17-19 January, 2024. [Presentation](#).

Updates

During the period M11-M13 (November and December 2023 and January 2024), five further ESIWACE3 Milestones have been published (and no Deliverables):

Milestones

- **Milestone 1.2: Roadmap and governance model for the HPCW**
M1.2 reports the roadmap adopted and the governance model for the High-Performance Climate and Weather Benchmark (HPCW). In particular, a steering group led by ESIWACE3 WP1 has been established to guide and monitor the scope, evolution and adoption of HPCW.
Read M1.2 [here](#).
- **Milestone 1.4: Applications developed by ESIWACE available to users of EuroHPC JU systems via automated deployment platform, including documentation for users, required software stack, automated testing and quality checks**
M1.4 lists the selected applications to be deployed in selected and accessible machines for the users of the EuroHC JU systems. To ensure and monitor the deployment, a steering group led by ESIWACE3 WP1 has been established, including partners responsible for the selected applications and the HPC centres of the consortiums supporting the target machines.
Read M1.4 [here](#).
- **Milestone 3.1: Strategy and Requirements for FDO-Standard in Simulation-based Climate Science**
M3.1 describes the strategy to follow and the requirements to effectively manage, share and analyse the massive and diverse datasets coming from climate science. It also lists the significant benefits that FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) can provide to the climate science

community, as well as the methodology, findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of implementing FDOs.

Read M3.1 [here](#).

- **Milestone 4.2: First call for projects in Service 2**

M4.2 states that the Call for Proposals for ESIWACE3 Service 2 was published and uploaded to the ESIWACE website. Service 2 deals with “State-of-the-art development tools for Weather and Climate” and aims to support the extensive preparations for the European ESM community. The call will run from 4 March 2024 until 3 June 2024.

Read M4.2 [here](#).

- **Milestone 5.2: The first hackathon organised**

M5.2 reports that the 1st ESIWACE3 hackathon was organised at the C-Tieteen Tietotekniikan Keskus OY (CSC) premises in Espoo (Finland) on 18-20 October 2023. Moreover, the ESIWACE3 hackathon was organised in tangent with a workshop organised in collaboration with eFlows4HPC and Climateurope2 to foster collaboration and knowledge transfer.

Read M5.2 [here](#).

News from the neighbours

Upcoming conferences and events

- [EuroHPC Summit](#), 18-21 March 2024, Antwerp (Belgium).
- [2024 Ocean Decade Conference](#), 10-12 April 2024, Barcelona (Spain).
- [European Geophysical Union Assembly](#), 14-19 April 2024, Vienna (Austria).
- [ISC24](#), 12-16 May 2024, Hamburg (Germany).
- [Teratec](#), 29-30 May 2024, Paris (France).
- [Advanced Computational Methods for Climate Modeling and Analysis minisymposium](#), 10-14 June 2024, Pilsen (Czech Republic).
- [Digital Ocean Forum](#), 14-15 June, 2024, Brussels (Belgium).

Training events

Find collected information on upcoming and past training events from all consortium partners and projects we are involved with [here](#).

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You can also look at the [previous issues](#) of the ESIWACE newsletter.